

12th ANNUAL REPORT
Year Ended June 30, 1968

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
1028 Connecticut Ave., N.W., Washington, D.C. 20036

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COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
JULY 1, 1967 — JUNE 30, 1968

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Director, Folger Shakespeare Library

¹Dr. Cole, by election on June 17, 1967, succeeded Mr. Clapp as President of the Council, effective September 1, 1967.

²Mr. Humphry and Mr. Vosper were elected Members of the Council on June 8, 1968.

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MELVILLE J. RUGGLES⁶

Consultant

VERNER W. CLAPP

³Dr. Cole, upon becoming President of the Council, succeeded Mr. Clapp as an ex-officio Member of the Executive Committee. Dr. Haskins, by election, succeeded Dr. Cole as a Member, November 18, 1967.

⁴Mrs. Oakes, whose resignation was effective June 14, 1968, was succeeded by Mr. Mehring as Acting Treasurer as of June 8, 1968.

⁵As of February 13, 1968.

⁶On leave of absence, to serve as staff director of the National Advisory Commission on Libraries, to January 1, 1968.

Consultant on Foreign Library Developments
SIR FRANK FRANCIS, K.C.B.

Senior Staff Members

LEE E. GROVE, *Director of Publications*
ROBERT T. JORDAN, *Library Specialist*⁷
LAWRENCE LIVINGSTON, *Systems Specialist*
CARL M. SPAULDING, *Systems Specialist*

Staff Member

RITA HILL, *Accountant*

⁷Until January 12, 1968.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

The Council on Library Resources, Inc., is an independent non-profit body incorporated in the District of Columbia with the principal objective of aiding in the solution of library problems. The Council, whose Members also constitute its Board of Directors, maintains its offices in Washington, D. C.

The Council was established in 1956 at the instance of the Ford Foundation with a grant of five million dollars, to be expended over a five-year period, "for the purpose of aiding in the solution of the problems of libraries generally and of research libraries in particular, conducting research in, developing and demonstrating new techniques and methods, and disseminating through any means the results thereof, and for making grants to other institutions and persons for such purposes; and for providing leadership in and wherever appropriate, coordination of efforts (1) to develop the resources and services of libraries and (2) to improve relations between American and foreign libraries and archives."

In 1960 and again in 1967 the Ford Foundation approved new grants totalling thirteen million dollars to enable the Council to carry forward its programs of research and demonstration toward the solution of library problems.

The Council conducts its work chiefly through grants or contracts to appropriate organizations or individuals. It welcomes proposals for work in furtherance of its objectives.

INTRODUCTION

The Year 1967-1968

From its inception the Council has been concerned with the efficiency of library services. For the long run the most promising means of achieving marked improvement in operations would seem to be through automation involving computers and other electronic data processing equipment. Unfortunately for librarians, most of the machines and procedures that have been available were developed by manufacturers and research and development organizations for enterprises other than libraries. The potential market for electronic equipment and automatic procedures tailored for libraries was considered to be too small to attract major attention of industry. Thus expensive and often inefficient and awkward adaptations were the principal resource for meeting library needs. Some changes in attitude among leading manufacturers have appeared, but there remains a wide gap between promise — implied or real — and delivery or application.

During the year which ended June 30, 1968, the Council made appropriations for the support of 31 new projects in a total amount of \$689,000. Additional sums were expended for programs previously approved. The projects are varied, as are the problems of libraries, but the projects related to automation are, in some respects, in the forefront. Of the 31 allocations somewhat less than a third concern automation, but these account for more than 71 per cent of the total appropriations. This not only suggests the Council's concern and interest in automation, as well as that of a good part of the library profession, but also underscores the fact that research and development in this area are expensive.

There are several intriguing aspects to library automation. There is the appeal of economies to be effected at a time when labor costs generally continue to increase and when there is a shortage of trained manpower. There is the attractive promise of being able to provide more service to an increasing population. And there is the heady dream that all the recorded experience and knowledge of the nation, if not that of the world, can be made readily available to anyone anywhere through automated networks and all-encompassing computer memories.

There is, too, an illusion abroad that all this and more is either possible now or just around the nearest corner. In the rhetoric of the automation enthusiasts it is easy to miss the qualifying word or phrase, if indeed such are used, and to suppose that all the technical and intellectual components of a system or systems are available and need only to be assembled. Or again, that what does not exist is susceptible to immediate development if only the right

people can be located and funded with the right amount of money. Unfortunately, this is not the case. Technicians who are familiar with the functions and functioning of libraries are rare. Funding of research and initial development, as extremely expensive as it is, is almost nothing compared to ongoing costs. This is particularly true of computer applications, for as suggested above, the paragons who combine extensive technical knowledge with sound library orientation are few and far between.

In sum, the new technology is expensive and uncertain, both the research and development and the equipment. Nevertheless, library problems will worsen and the remedies grow more costly if the subject of automation is neglected today. Thus, the Council will continue to support with due caution promising programs leading to further automation of library services. It will encourage cost projections and cost benefit studies in the projects it supports as well as in those supported by others. It will continue to serve as best it can as a catalyst in encouraging an understanding of the problems of libraries and their potential solutions through automation. And it will continue to hope that industry and private profit-making corporations will show greater initiative in the future regarding libraries, thus demonstrating a concern for the public welfare and their own long-term interest.

FRED C. COLE
President

Projects Commenced or Completed 1967-1968

I. ARCHIVES

Archives: The proper housing and preservation of permanently valuable records are today major concerns of historical societies, libraries, private industry, and all levels of government. In order that future planners may profit from the experiences of the recent past, a grant has been made to the Society of American Archivists to assist publication of a selection of papers relating to the programming, planning and functional equipment of the archives and record center buildings erected in the United States in the middle third of the century. The compilation is being prepared by Victor Gondos, Jr., chairman of the Society's Committee on Archival Buildings and Equipment, who has been both architect and archivist.

Status of the National Archives The National Archives and Records Service of the General Services Administration is "responsible for selecting, preserving, and making available to the Government and to the public the permanently valuable non-current records of the Federal Government and for promoting improved current records management and paperwork practices in Federal agencies."¹ There are approximately 900,000 cubic feet of such records, ranging in date from 1774 to the 1960's, whose importance to historians, economists, political scientists, and others cannot be exaggerated. The Council of the American Historical Association in December 1966 established a joint committee with the Organization of American Historians and the Society of American Archivists to study and report on the status of the National Archives. The Council on Library Resources, as previously reported, made a grant to assist the inquiry.² The committee's work has been substantially completed and publication of a report is expected late in 1968.

II. AUTOMATION

Journal of Library Automation The preceding annual report noted a grant to the American Library Association enabling its then newly established Information Science and Automation Division to publish a journal.³ "Volume I, Number 1" and "Number 2" of the *Journal of Library Automation*

¹ *United States Government Organization Manual 1967-68*. Revised June 1, 1967. p. 474.

² XI: 10-11. Citations in this form refer to the Council's annual reports; in this case to the 11th Annual Report, pages 10-11.

³ XI: 15-16.

— dated March and June 1968, respectively — appeared this year. The quarterly is expected to become self-supporting at the end of three years. It is devoted exclusively to professional articles in the field and is abstracted in *Chemical Abstracts*, *Computing Reviews*, *Documentation Abstracts* and *Library Science Abstracts*.

**New England
Board of
Higher Education**

Work has continued on the development of a regional computer-based library center to serve the libraries of the state-supported universities united in the New England Board of Higher Education, a project described in the preceding annual report.⁴ In April 1968 the University of Maine withdrew on the ground that it could not contribute the staff time and funds that it felt would soon be required, but the presidents of the universities of Connecticut, Massachusetts, New Hampshire, Rhode Island, and Vermont have reaffirmed their continuing interest and the Council this past May made a fourth grant to further the work.⁵

Pilot operation began the end of December 1967 when the University of New Hampshire became the first member of the network to become connected with the center, located in Cambridge, Massachusetts. Currently, printed catalog cards and book labels are being experimentally produced for the participating libraries. Present indications are that the system will be fully operational at the beginning of 1970 and capable of serving as many as 24 libraries. Compatibility with Project MARC for machine-readable cataloging information from the Library of Congress is planned.

⁴XI: 12-14.

⁵For a general account of the project see: Donald E. Vincent, "New England State University Libraries' Regional Processing Center." *ALA Bulletin* 61: 672-3, June 1967.

The overall specifications are described in: Inforonics, Inc.: *Development of a Computer Processing Center for the New England State University Libraries, Submitted to the New England Board of Higher Education and the Council on Library Resources*. Cambridge, Massachusetts, July 13, 1967. [4] 25, 8, 19, 5 p. 28 cms.

Incident to the above study was the need to know the percentage of overlap in the several library collections. For this see: William R. Nugent, "Statistics of Collection Overlap at the Libraries of the Six New England State Universities." *Library Resources & Technical Services* 12: 31-36, Winter 1968.

Other reports include:

NELINET — *New England Library Information Network. Catalog Data File Creation for the New England Regional Library Technical Processing Center*. Prepared by James E. Agenbroad, Donald D. Hodgins, Robert H. Simmons. Submitted to the New England Board of Higher Education. *Final Report of CLR-374*. June 20, 1968. Cambridge, Massachusetts, 1968. [62] l. 28 cms.

NELINET — *New England Library Information Network. Progress Report, July 1, 1967-March 30, 1968. Systems Design and Pilot Operation of a Regional Center for Technical Processing for the Libraries of the New England State Universities*. Prepared by James E. Agenbroad, Lawrence F. Buckland, Ann T. Curran, Donald D. Hodgins, William R. Nugent, Robert H. Simmons. Submitted to The New England Board of Higher Education. *Final Report, Contract No. CLR-385*. April 5, 1968. Inforonics, Inc., Cambridge, Massachusetts, 1968. Volume 1, 38 l.; II, Appendices [167] l. 28 cms.

Project Intrex (Information Transfer Experiments) is an ambitious investigation at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology of bases on which the technical library of the future may be modeled. In January 1967 the Council made a grant to support preliminary work in one of several planned areas of research — a text-access program.⁶

Primarily, the information contained in libraries is in the form of printed documents or of photographic images of document pages in microform. While future libraries will store some of their information in digitally encoded form, the bulk of their holdings will continue to be in graphic form. An efficient information transfer network must provide access to such information at remote terminals. A reader will wish to have material from the central store displayed, either for brief examination or for lengthy study, and he will wish for the opportunity to obtain a copy to keep. Another requirement is that the text-access system provide rapid service, even if several readers simultaneously ask for the same material.⁷

After consultation with an advisory panel established by the Council with the approval of M.I.T.,⁸ the Council in May made an interim grant so that the Project might continue in operation through the summer months. The grant was broadened to include work on the augmented catalog. The purposes of this program, which had received previous support from the National Science Foundation and other sources, is to develop and operationally test a remote-access computer-based catalog, augmented with respect to a conventional catalog in its breadth of document coverage, depth of information on each entry, and the interactive manner in which users can easily search and retrieve information.

It should be noted that the programs of Project Intrex are in the nature of basic research; it may be a considerable time before libraries generally derive benefits from the experiments.

Project MARC The Council's role in the initial development of the MARC (Machine Readable Cataloging) Project, to test the feasibility of distributing Library of Congress cataloging information in machine-readable form to a variety of

⁶XI: 14-15.

⁷Reports of work on the Text-Access Program will be found in the following: Massachusetts Institute of Technology: Project Intrex. *Semiannual Activity Report, 15 March 1967 to 15 September 1967. PR-4, 15 September 1967.* Cambridge, Massachusetts, [1967], p. 31-46, and in the *Semiannual Activity Report, 15 September 1967 to 15 March 1968. PR-5, 15 March 1968, p. 36-54.*

⁸The members of the committee are: William O. Baker, Vice President for Research and Development, Bell Telephone Laboratories; Harvey Brooks, Dean, Division of Engineering and Applied Physics, Harvard University; Melvin Day, Deputy Assistant Administrator for Technology Utilization, National Aeronautics and Space Administration; Herman H. Henkle, Executive Director, John Crerar Library; Emmanuel R. Piore, Vice President for Research and Development, International Business Machines Corporation; Merton P. Stoltz, Provost, Brown University; and Robert Vosper, University Librarian, University of California, Los Angeles.

libraries, has been told in preceding annual reports.⁹ The success of the pilot project encouraged further improvements, which resulted in the development of the new MARC II format for bibliographical information on tape. A Council-supported report has been published.¹⁰ The Council this year made a grant to defray expenses incident to a meeting of project participants to discuss the then proposed new format and other technical aspects of the next stage of development. A report of this meeting has been issued.¹¹ The MARC II format has been approved as a standard by the Information Science and Automation, Resources and Technical Services, and Reference Service divisions of the American Library Association; it has also been adopted by the three national libraries. The Library of Congress is expected to begin operating its MARC Distribution Service early next year. Abroad, a British National Bibliography MARC project is planned for sometime in 1968. Thus an international exchange of compatible tapes on a regular basis in the future seems to be assured.

The three National Libraries One of the major developments for libraries in the field of automation was the creation in May 1967 of a joint Task Force on Automation and Other Cooperative Services by the National Library of Medicine, National Agricultural Library and Library of Congress.

The Task Force represents a systems approach to the establishment of an automated network of library service; obviously significant problems relate to compatibility arising from the various products and services each of the three libraries provides.

As the Task Force moved ahead, the National Library of Medicine found that because of staff resources it was unable to accomplish the work expected of it. An appeal was made to the Council for assistance. In view of the importance of the joint project, the Council has employed an experienced systems specialist and assigned him to Task Force duties at the Library of Medicine. Arrangements for other appropriate assistance to the Task Force have been made.

National Serials Data Program Serials are one of the most important parts of library collections; they are indispensable to research in the fields of science and technology, humanities, and social sciences. Serials are also difficult to control bibliographically. The data elements are subject to frequent

⁹X: 29-30, 41-42; XI: 11-12.

¹⁰*The MARC II Format, A Communications Format For Bibliographic Data.* Prepared by Henriette D. Avram, John F. Knapp, and Lucia J. Rather. Information Systems Office, Library of Congress, Washington, D. C. January 1968. [iv, 167] p. 26 cms. Processed.

¹¹*Proceedings of the Fourth Conference on Machine-Readable Catalog Copy. Library of Congress December 4, 1967. Sponsored by the Council on Library Resources, Inc. Washington, D. C. Library of Congress, 1968. i, 11 1. 26½ cms. And: Supplement One, The MARC II Format.* Henriette B. Avram, John F. Knapp, and Lucia J. Rather. Information Systems Office, Library of Congress, Washington, 1968. 7 p.

change and require constant updating; titles are often difficult to identify, describe, and locate. In 1957 the Joint Committee on the Union List of Serials described a plan developed by Wyllis E. Wright, Williams College librarian, for placing and maintaining the Union List on punched cards. The plan was ahead of its time, and prohibitively expensive. Today, with computer technology, what was then not practical may be feasible — to wit, an exhaustive, continuously updated central record of serial publications and their library locations, capable of providing regional union lists and similar materials. In June 1967 the Library of Congress began work on such a project — the National Serials Data Program — under contract to the Joint Committee on the Union List of Serials with funding from the National Library of Medicine, National Agricultural Library, and the National Science Foundation. This past May the Council made an appropriation to assist in the development of a national data bank of machine-readable information on all serial publications, a major objective in the joint automation program of the three national libraries.

Automated Control of Thematic Maps With more than three million maps, the cartographic collections of the Library of Congress rank among the two or three greatest in the world in terms of volume, scope, and quality.

Unfortunately, the maps are neither organized nor serviced as effectively as they should be, and the very magnitude of the collections makes an attempt at more adequate manual bibliographical controls impractical. The progressing development of automated controls for library materials, however, has made it appear feasible to develop controls for newly acquired single-sheet maps, which arrive at a rate of more than 30,000 each year. If this is done, within a few years the maps under control will comprise a significant part of the total holdings. A Council grant this year enabled the Library's Geography and Map Division, in cooperation with the Information Systems Office, to develop procedures for automated control of thematic maps. This is expected to lead to improved reference service and to distribution of the bibliographic information to other libraries as in Project MARC.

Classification Scheme for Slides A grant has also been made to the University of California, Santa Cruz, for the development of a machine-manipulable universal classification scheme for its collection of some 30,000 slides

and of a computer-produced catalog in book form. The project involves the use of punched cards and relatively low level data processing equipment. The use of multiple "access points" in a 15-digit number will make it possible to produce machine print-outs under a variety of headings, such as date, location, personal name, and subject. The classification scheme is expected to accommodate visual materials of all academic disciplines and to be of use in published form to other libraries having slide collections.

Optical Scanning The Los Angeles Public Library, the fifth largest public library in the United States, received a grant from the Council in 1966 to assist it in an investigation of optical character recognition as an input method for use with computer-based library systems. The project has been completed and a report issued.¹² The report discusses optical character readers and library input requirements, and the relative costs of alternative methods. It also describes the demonstration systems developed—for catalog production, circulation control, registration control, and an acquisition system conceptually designed but not implemented—and the operation and results of the page reader and document reader demonstrations. The information resulting from the investigation is being used by the Library in the design and implementation of a computerized book catalog production system with optical character recognition as the input method.

A Computer Center for Five District of Columbia University Libraries The Consortium of Universities of Washington, D. C., consists of American, Catholic, Georgetown, George Washington, and Howard universities.

Within the framework of the Consortium is the Interuniversity Library Council, which serves to coordinate the work of the member libraries in such matters as building collections and revision of a union list of serials. Would a joint computer center benefit the five libraries? The Council made a grant to Georgetown University in behalf of the Interuniversity Council for a feasibility study.¹³ Dr. Ralph H. Parker, Director of Libraries at the University of Missouri, and an expert on the subject of library computerization, was employed to make the study. His report¹⁴ concludes that of four alternatives the most practical at this time would be a jointly operated small to medium sized computer operated in batch mode with basic records maintained on tapes.

Costs of Converting Bibliographic Data to Machine-Readable Form A previous annual report cited a grant to Michigan State University for a cost comparison of three methods of converting to machine-readable form its shelf list of some 6,000 cards, with the initial purpose of establishing an automated book-charging system.¹⁵ The investigation

¹²X: 42-43. The report: Los Angeles County Public Library. *An Optical Character Research and Demonstration Project*. The Library, [1968]. v, 88 p. 28 cms.

¹³XI: 16.

¹⁴Ralph Parker. *A Feasibility Study for a Joint Computer Center for Five Washington, D. C. University Libraries. Final Report*. [Washington,] Consortium of Universities of Metropolitan Washington, D. C. May, 1968. 11, 37 p. 28 cms. See also: Joseph E. Jeffs, "Five Libraries in Search of a Computer: Expanding University Cooperation." *D. C. Libraries* 39: 47-52, Summer 1968.

¹⁵X: 42.

has been concluded and a report published.¹⁶ The three methods studied were key punching, optical scanning by a service bureau, and paper-tape typewriting. The cost of the first two methods is the same, it was found, but conversion by paper-tape typewriter is more expensive.

Computer-Controlled Typographic Composition The results of a grant to the National Bureau of Standards to design and run tests of computer-controlled photocomposition of various kinds of bibliographic records have also been published.¹⁷ The investigation centered on a versatile Mergenthaler-Linofilm-Autoset computer program. The report concludes that Autoset composition is practical and notes its use at the Government Printing Office for the Library of Congress subject headings system.

III. BIBLIOGRAPHIES

American Imprints Believing bibliographies in general to be outside its special fields of interest, the Council seldom gives assistance in their preparation or publication, other than those of such considerable significance as the *National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections* and the *Union List of Serials*. This year, however, a small grant was made to Richard H. Shoemaker, Professor of Library Science at Rutgers — The State University. The grant provided Professor Shoemaker with clerical assistance and funds for photoduplication so that he might devote an unexpected term of leave to continuing work on his *Checklist of American Imprints* of the early nineteenth century. Earlier volumes had already been published. The work is helping to fill a gap in the national bibliography.

New Serial Titles The five-volume third edition of the *Union List of Serials in Libraries in the United States and Canada*, issued at the beginning of 1966, provides a consolidated record of the serial holdings of North American libraries as of about that time. The vehicle for continuing the record is *New Serial Titles*, a monthly publication of the Library of Congress since 1959 with periodic cumulations. It provides a record of the location of serials that started publication after 1949 in the United

¹⁶ Richard E. Chapin and Dale H. Pretzer. "Comparative Costs of Converting Shelf List Records to Machine Readable Form." *Journal of Library Automation* 1: 66-74, March 1968.

¹⁷X:43. The report: National Bureau of Standards Report, NBS Project 4556141, NBS Report 9598, May 1967. *Study of and Experimentation in Computer Composition of Library Materials*, by Roy W. Worrall and Roberta H. Larkin . . . To Council on Library Resources. [Washington], U. S. Department of Commerce, National Bureau of Standards. vi, 84 p. 26½ cms.

States and Canada. In view of the importance of serials for research, a grant was made to the Joint Committee on the Union List of Serials for a study of the effectiveness of *New Serial Titles* as a bibliographical tool and record.¹⁸ The study, under the direction of A. Frederick Kuhlman, Director Emeritus of the Joint University Libraries, Nashville, has been completed.¹⁹ Questionnaires were returned by 749 institutions subscribing to and/or participating in *New Serial Titles*. The results were most satisfactory; useful suggestions for improvement in coverage, bibliographical listing, and other matters were obtained and it was found that there is general approval of the publication.

IV. BOOK SELECTION AND PROCUREMENT

Legal Literature The Council this year made a second supplemental grant to the Association of American Law Schools for preparation of book selection lists for law school libraries.²⁰ The lists indicate the recommended priority of titles for purchase in various categories of Anglo-American, foreign, international, and comparative law, and are prepared for the guidance of libraries of varying size. Publication of the subject lists, in looseleaf form, is well under way and it is believed that all will be issued before 1970.²¹

Chinese Research Materials One of the results of World War II and other Far Eastern involvements has been the continuing growth of Oriental studies, with consequent demands for better research collections. This has presented a problem for libraries, for not only is the material expensive but much of it is very difficult to obtain. To assist in finding a solution, the Council made a grant in 1965 to the Association for Asian Studies, Inc., with headquarters at the University of Michigan, toward the establishment of a Chinese Materials and Research Aids Center in Taiwan.²² The Center's staff has since grown from three to more than twenty to handle the republication of out-of-print scholarly materials, preparation of bibliographical research aids, acquisitions, and other services. A thousand libraries in

¹⁸ XI: 18.

¹⁹ A. F. Kuhlman. *A Report on the Consumer Survey of New Serial Titles, Made for the Joint Committee on The Union List of Serials, Inc., and the Library of Congress under a Grant from the Council on Library Resources, Inc.* [No place,] August 1, 1967. vii, 84 p. 28 cms.

²⁰ Previous grants were reported in VIII: 18-19 and X: 17-18, 44.

²¹ *Association of American Law Schools. Law Books Recommended for Libraries. No. 1, Introduction.* South Hackensack, New Jersey, Fred B. Rothman & Company, 1967. 5 l. 28 cms. A third of the approximately 45 subject lists projected has been published.

²² IX: 35.

North America, the Middle East, Europe and Asia are receiving its mailings.²³ The Center is now independent of Council aid.

V. CATALOGING AND INDEXING

Spanish Subject Headings Latin American libraries have long suffered from the absence of a standard list of subject headings for use in organizing collections and catalogs. With each library making its own list of headings, the result has been lack of uniformity among libraries, wasted time, and some illogicity. To remedy the deficiency, the Council in 1964 made a grant to the Pan American Union toward the preparation of a subject heading list in Spanish.²⁴ This has now been completed and published in an edition of 2000 copies for free distribution to Latin American libraries and library schools in the United States.²⁵ The list is regarded as a landmark in the development of Latin American libraries and is expected to effect savings of \$200,000 to \$500,000 per annum in cataloging costs.

Cataloging Rules for Publications in Hindi Although Hindi is among the languages of the world in which the greatest number of books is published, there is no established code of rules in India or elsewhere for cataloging books in Hindi, nor is there any standard practice among Indian publishers in giving publication details. Cataloging problems are further heightened by the different usage of Indian names in various linguistic areas of India, by the variation in transliterated forms in which names appear, and by the great freedom exercised by the individual in his treatment of his own name. Through a grant to University College, London, M. R. Jain, an experienced librarian, is preparing a cataloging code for materials in Hindi as part of his work for a graduate degree in the School of Librarianship and Archives. J. D. Pearson, Librarian of the School of Oriental and African Studies, is in charge of the project.

VI. LIBRARY ADMINISTRATION

Pilferage Thefts from the collections of public and academic libraries represent a serious and widespread problem. Just how serious no one knows,²⁶ but some institutions have

²³ "Council on Library Resources Grant." *Newsletter of the Association for Asian Studies* 13: 1, October 1967.

²⁴ VIII: 16.

²⁵ *Lista de Encabezamientos de Materia para Bibliotecas*. Compilada por Carmen Rovira y Jorge Aguayo. Union Panamericana, Washington, D. C., 1967. Volume I, iv, 191; II, iii, 450; III, xx, 436 p. 27 cm.

²⁶ The preceding annual report (XI: 26) noted a grant from the Council for an investigation of the extent of the problem.

estimated their losses as up to five per cent of their collections annually. In May 1967 the Free Library of Philadelphia began field-testing in its Frankford branch of a theft prevention system, "Checkpoint." Preliminary experience with the system, developed by the Logistics Industries Corporation, of Philadelphia, indicated that it had great promise but needed further refinement. The Council has therefore made a grant to enable the Free Library to extend testing to three additional branches. According to an interim report, losses have declined substantially and the savings thus realized more than compensate for the system's cost. The reaction of patrons, who are aware of the system and pleased to find more books on the shelves, has also been encouraging.

Libraries and Graduate Education

What are the characteristics of library collections which contribute to scholarship and graduate-level training in research? Curiously, there have not been many attempts to relate the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of academic libraries to achievement in the graduate programs they support. When attempts have been made they have but seldom led to recommendations or standards for the kinds of library collections such programs require. A grant has been made to enable two Purdue University men — John H. Moriarty, Director of University Libraries and Audio-Visual Center, and Warren F. Seibert, Head of the Instructional Media Research Unit — to design a study aimed at identifying the characteristics of libraries and subject collections which have the most relevance for achievement in graduate education.

PASSING THROUGH "CHECKPOINT" at the circulation desk in the Frankford Branch of the Free Library of Philadelphia. The heavy framed cases represent "Checkpoint."

Machine Instruction in Library Use Several years ago the Council made a grant to Mt. San Antonio College in Walnut, California, to experiment with teaching machines for instruction of students in the use of the library.²⁷ The machines were programmed to show slides of various library areas while an audio tape described their use. The results were mixed. Although the machines saved time for the librarians, they were too expensive for the average library. Further, they did not hold up very well under continuous use, and the control board was too complicated for the average student. The Council this year made a new grant to Mt. San Antonio for design of a prototype machine which may remedy the deficiencies of the original equipment and be suitable for commercial manufacture for use in other academic libraries.

Library Lighting There is a variety of opinions as to what is the proper level of lighting for libraries. In an effort to arrive at a definitive answer, the Association of Research Libraries has asked Keyes D. Metcalf, Librarian of Harvard College Emeritus, to inquire into the subject, and the Council has made a grant for the purpose. Mr. Metcalf has been associated with building or remodeling projects during much of his long career in library work and is the author of a comprehensive manual on the planning and construction of academic libraries.²⁸

ALA International Relations In order to handle the volume of business with the Federal Government and establish closer contact with other private organizations working in the international book and library field, the American Library Association has moved some of the functions of its International Relations Office from Chicago to Washington. The Council has made a grant toward the support of the Office for a year marked by unusual administrative expenses stemming from the opening of the new location. The Chicago office continues to program and direct the study visits of foreign librarians to the United States, to handle inquiries from abroad regarding training for librarianship, and to maintain a roster of American librarians available for overseas assignments.

American Library Laws The obsolescence of the second edition of *American Library Laws*, published in 1943, prompted the Council to make a grant to the American Library Association for the compilation of a new edition by Alex Ladenson, Assistant Librarian of the Chicago Public Library and a member of the Illinois Bar.²⁹ The third edition was published

²⁷ VIII: 36-37; XI: 27.

²⁸ *Planning Academic and Research Library Buildings. Sponsored by the Association of Research Libraries and the Association of College and Research Libraries Under a Grant By the Council on Library Resources.* New York, McGraw-Hill Book Company, [1965].

²⁹ VII: 32. See also: IX: 38; X: 16.

in 1964 and includes within its 1,599 pages all laws in effect as of December 31, 1962, pertaining to libraries of the Federal Government, the 50 states, and the territories and dependencies. Terms of the grant specified that revenues derived from sale of the volume be used for supplements. A *First Supplement* was published in 1965, and another was issued this past year.³⁰

New York World's Fair The Council in 1962 made a grant enabling an American Library Association/New York World's Fair Advisory Committee to determine the feasibility of participation in the then forthcoming Fair; a subsequent grant in 1964 provided "scholarships" for 20 of the 267 professional librarians who staffed the library exhibit at various times in the United States Pavilion.³¹ The exhibit, "Library/USA," attracted some two million visitors during the 360 days of its operation, and a report has now been published.³²

New York: METRO The New York Metropolitan Reference and Research Library Agency, chartered by the New York Board of Regents, is a non-profit cooperative organization. It provides an Interlibrary Center offering easy access to information sources of all kinds and engages in special projects such as in-service training, studies of various types, and reports on legislative, technical, and other developments affecting library work. A grant from the Council made possible the formation of a small secretariat in 1966 and defrayed its expenses for a year.³³ During this period 50 libraries in the area affiliated with METRO on a dues-paying basis.

University Library Standards Is it possible to evaluate a university library? How should it be done? These were questions considered at a Council-assisted two-day joint meeting of committees of the Association of College and Research Libraries and the Association of Research Libraries. The groups met in November 1967 at Boston University to discuss the feasibility of constructing standards for university libraries as well as statistical and other aspects of the questions. The meeting resulted in the formation of a committee representing both organizations to pursue the problem.

³⁰ Alex Ladenson, editor. *American Library Laws, Third Edition, Second Supplement, 1965-1966*. Chicago, American Library Association, 1967. 267 p. 27 cm.

³¹ VIII: 47-48; IX: 46-47.

³² Gordon P. Martin, Joseph Becker, Alphonse F. Trezza, *Library/USA, A Bibliographic and Descriptive Report*. Chicago, American Library Association, 1967. 192 p.

³³ X: 60. See also: VIII: 47.

VII. PHOTOGRAPHIC APPLICATIONS

Evaluation of Microform Readers A grant to the American Library Association this year enabled its Library Technology Program to arrange with William R. Hawken Associates for a series of evaluations of microform readers. Reports on five readers were published in the March 1968 issue of *Library Technology Reports*, and on two more in the May issue. Evaluations of three other readers were to be published in the September issue. The reports evaluate the equipment in terms of such characteristics as construction, power requirements, and capability.

International Guide to Micrographic Equipment The Council's Tenth Report recorded a grant to the International Micrographic Congress for the preparation and publication of an international directory to micrographic equipment.³⁴ The directory has now been published.³⁵ It complements the National Microfilm Association's *Guide to Microproduction Equipment*, established in 1959 with assistance from the Council³⁶ and now in a third edition. As with the *Guide*, which is limited to equipment manufactured or distributed in the United States, receipts from sale of the *International Directory* are to be used for new editions.

VIII. PHYSICAL ACCESS

Telefacsimile and Libraries "The *St. Louis Practical Photographer* for March 1880 quotes a Pittsburgh correspondent on the work of T. A. Connolly and a 'Mr. McTighe' (whether J. J. or T. J. McTighe, both electrical inventors of the time, is not stated) as follows

"... by his experiments he has been able to reproduce clearly and faithfully, in a dark room at his residence, the images of persons at the other end of the line, extending from another part of the house ...

"... the inventors believe that they will be able to transmit *instantaneously*, from point to point, any written or printed document, as for instance one entire side of a newspaper ..."³⁷

³⁴ X: 51.

³⁵ Jack Rubin, editor. *International Directory of Micrographic Equipment. First Edition.* Saratoga, California, International Micrographic Congress, 1967. 519 p. 22 cm.

³⁶ III: 37; X: 22, 51.

³⁷ Quoted from "Telefacsimile in 1880." [By Paul Vanderbilt] *Library of Congress Information Bulletin* 10: 37 (September 10, 1951) p. 7.

Nearly ninety years have elapsed since Connolly and McTighe were anticipating the use of telefacsimile, and it has yet to become a useful library tool. Such practical problems as cost and the inability to transmit material satisfactorily from bound books have stood in the way. In the past decade the Council has aided several investigations of the subject, and one was noted in the previous annual report.³⁸ This involved the experimental use of telefacsimile to link the libraries of the Reno and Las Vegas campuses of the University of Nevada and the Davis campus of the University of California. The resulting report discussed equipment, inter-campus loan procedures, and costs.³⁹ Interest at Nevada continued high and a further inquiry was conducted, this time a comparative evaluation of three systems — Xerox Magnavox Telecopier (the equipment used in the original investigation), Datafax 1824 and Dial/Datafax, and Alden 11 Docufax. The report of this inquiry provides comparative information about the equipment in terms of general operating principles, speed, reliability, copy quality, and cost.⁴⁰

Another outgrowth of the earlier experiment was expansion of the program in California. Two grants were made to extend the investigation from the Davis branch to the University of California Berkeley campus. Long Distance Xerography equipment was used, and particular attention was given to developing procedures for faster intercampus interlibrary loan service. The experimenters concluded that already existing procedures for interlibrary loans should be reorganized and made to function smoothly with surface transport before the investment in telefacsimile equipment is made. Late in 1967 the Council made a third grant for publication of a larger edition of the report.⁴¹

Home Delivery of Books Home delivery of books dates back to at least the nineteenth century but, except for shut-ins and members of a few subscription libraries, such service has faded away in the present century. However, there has been recent renewal of interest in the idea, and in 1961 the Council made a grant for a trial.⁴² Because of extraneous factors the results were inconclusive, but the idea persisted and

³⁸ See "Telecommunication," X: 49, 116-7; another was reported in the next annual report, XI: 29.

³⁹ H. G. Morehouse. *Telefacsimile Services Between Libraries With the Xerox Magnavox Telecopier* . . . A study prepared for the Council on Library Resources, Inc. . . . Reno, University of Nevada Library, 1966. 54 p. 28 cms.

⁴⁰ H. G. Morehouse. *Equipment for Facsimile Transmission Between Libraries; a Description and Comparative Evaluation of Three Systems*. A Study Prepared for the Council on Library Resources, Inc. December 29, 1967. Reno, University of Nevada Library, [1968]. 28 p. 28 cm.

⁴¹ William D. Scheiber and Ralph M. Shoffner. *Telefacsimile in Libraries: A Report of an Experiment in Facsimile Transmission and an Analysis of Implications for Interlibrary Loan Systems*. [Berkeley], Institute of Library Research, University of California, February 1968. v, 137 p. 28 cms.

⁴² VI: 32; XI: 29-30.

was the subject of a four-day meeting during the American Library Association's annual conference in June 1967. The interest shown there prompted the Council to make a grant to the San Antonio Public Library System to explore the feasibility of books by mail as a regular feature of public library service in San Antonio and Bexar County, Texas.

During the experiment, anyone who does not owe fines on overdue books can expect books to be mailed to him at his home within 24 hours of his telephoned request. San Antonio Public absorbs the cost of postage and other incidental expenses on outgoing packages. Return of the books is the responsibility of the borrower. Costs are to be compared with those of conventional walk-in service to ascertain whether free mailing can realistically become a part of the services offered by the San Antonio Public Library System.

High Reduction Microphotography An ultra-fiche storage and retrieval system is one using sheet microfilm (or chips) with reduction ratios in excess of 100:1. The possibility of using this kind of system for the storage and dissemination of library materials, particularly seldom-used materials, is an attractive one if problems like optical satisfaction, efficiency, and cost can be acceptably met. Techniques developed by the Republic Aviation Division, Fairchild Hiller Corporation, appeared to offer the possibility of adaptation to library purposes. The Council

MAILING DESK AT THE SAN ANTONIO PUBLIC LIBRARY, where books are sent to patrons' homes in response to telephoned requests.

accordingly contracted in 1966 for an investigation.⁴³ However, microphotography at high reduction involves technical problems not present in systems utilizing lower reduction ratios. It was found that the readability of images produced was not satisfactory for the purpose, and this and some other physical limitations made the system unsuitable for library application.

IX. PLANNING

Copyright Revision For more than a decade major efforts have been under way to effect a long overdue general revision of the Copyright Act of 1909. Libraries, as well as authors and publishers, will be affected. One of the chief services of libraries is to facilitate copying for scholarly use, and the increasing use of photocopying for this purpose has given rise to many copyright questions for libraries. The American Library Association's Committee on Copyright Issues was charged with making policy and action recommendations to the Association's executive board and council with regard to legislation being developed in the Congress, and the Council made a grant this past year to defray the cost of several needed legal studies.

Needs of Research Libraries At the request of the National Advisory Commission on Libraries, appointed by President Johnson in September 1966 to provide in the course of a year a national plan for library development, the American Council of Learned Societies has prepared a report on the needs of research libraries. The work was funded by the Council on Library Resources⁴⁴ and represents the thinking of a distinguished advisory and working group. The report has been completed and submitted to the Commission for its use. It is planned that the "Statement and Recommendations of the Committee on Research Libraries of the American Council of Learned Societies" will be published.

Education for Librarianship As a feature of the centennial observance of the University of Illinois, its Graduate School of Library Science held an international conference on the theme of "Education for Librarianship" in June 1967. Fifty-eight persons, representing schools of librarianship and libraries

⁴³X: 50.

⁴⁴XI: 30-31.

in many parts of the world, attended the meeting, which was assisted by a grant from the Council.⁴⁵ The development of library education, the organization and operation of library schools, curriculum principles and practices, teaching methods, and advanced study in librarianship were the subjects of the five-day meeting. The 20 papers given at the conference have now been published.⁴⁶

Flooded Italian Libraries In November 1966 storms caused the worst floods to occur in Italy since World War II. Among the catastrophic effects was severe damage to the great collections of the Florentine libraries. Although restoration work began almost instantly, it is a slow and painstaking task expected to require some years. In July 1967 the Council made a grant to the American Library Association to enable Arthur T. Hamlin to visit Florence and report on conditions. Mr. Hamlin, Librarian at the University of Cincinnati and chairman of a Special Committee on Aid to Italian Libraries of the Association's International Relations Committee, has made his report to the Special Committee.

Arizona Library Survey The Arizona State Department of Library and Archives, in an effort to improve the substandard library service available in the State, commissioned a survey from the Bureau of Educational Research and Services of the College of Education, Arizona State University. This was followed by a May 1967 seminar in Chandler to explain and advance the recommendations resulting from the statewide library survey. As related in the previous annual report, the Council made a grant to the University for this purpose.⁴⁷ Three publications have resulted: a report of the findings of the survey, another on school libraries, and a campaign brochure for distribution to librarians, trustees, and other influential persons.⁴⁸

⁴⁵ XI: 32-33.

⁴⁶ Larry Earl Bone, editor. *Library Education: An International Survey*. [Urbana, Illinois], University of Illinois Graduate School of Library Science, [1968]. xiii, 388 p.

⁴⁷ XI: 32.

⁴⁸ Grace Thomas Stevenson. *Arizona Library Survey. A Comprehensive Study of Library Service in Arizona with a Projection for Future Services*. Harold E. Moore, Coordinator of the Survey. [Tempe], The Bureau of Educational Research and Services, College of Education, Arizona State University, January 1968. xi, 272 p. 28 cms.

Melvin Glenn Guthrie. *A Study of Conditions and Services in School Libraries in the State of Arizona. A Supplementary Report of the Arizona Library Survey . . .* Tempe, Bureau of Educational Research and Services, College of Education, Arizona State University, January 1968. xvii, 247 p. 28 cms.

[Dickson Hartwell]. *A Candid Appraisal of Libraries in Arizona*. [No place], Arizona Department of Library and Archives, Arizona State Library Association, [No date]. 8 p. 23 cms.

X. PRESERVATION OF LIBRARY MATERIALS

A National Plan for Preservation of Deteriorating Research Materials The various steps in the development of a national plan for the preservation of deteriorating research materials in American libraries (some 3 billion pages if only a single copy of each item is involved) have been related before.⁴⁹ Suffice it to say here that the Association of Research Libraries has taken the initiative in seeking such a program and that a Council grant has enabled it to arrange with the Library of Congress, one of its 80 members, for a pilot project. The Library, incidentally, had for several years been segregating its brittle books and microfilming thousands of titles otherwise beyond redemption. Central to the proposed national program is the intention of preserving in some location the best available copy of each deteriorating title. This prompts such questions as how to identify the copy in best condition, the definition of "best," the methods of preservation, and the bibliographical control of this material.

The pilot project has been completed and a report distributed to members of the Association of Research Libraries.⁵⁰ In the course of the project procedures were developed for comparing titles in the Library's brittle book collection with the same titles in other libraries, some basis for cost estimates was established, and other factors explored or discovered. A general conclusion

⁴⁹ See XI: 33-34.

⁵⁰ *Library of Congress Pilot Project, Final Report, 30 November 1967. 7 l. 27 cms.*

BRITTLE BOOKS are removed from the shelves of the Library of Congress for segregation.

of the report is that a national preservation collection is administratively feasible. Problems of implementation, outside the scope of the pilot project, remain. One of these is the need for an inexpensive method of deacidifying books, another is to ascertain the proper humidity and temperature for storage—all subjects requiring more investigation. In due course a decision will have to be made as to the location of the national preservation collection. A building or cave equipped for the purpose? And where? Finally, funds will have to be found for the preservation program and center, admittedly so expensive a project that the only justification is the need to prevent much of the record of man's experience, knowledge, and imagination from crumbling away within a short time.

The Barrow Research Laboratory Much of the credit for focusing attention in recent years on the widespread deterioration of the books in our libraries is due to William J. Barrow and the laboratory to which he gave his name. Although Mr. Barrow's death in August 1967 terminated an association with the Council which had begun a decade earlier,⁵¹ the Council has continued its relationship with the W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory. Dr. Robert N. DuPuis has served as acting director and Dr. Reavis Sproull as technical consultant, both on a part-time basis. Dr. DuPuis is a research chemist and formerly director of research for the Philip Morris Tobacco Company and for General Foods. Dr. Sproull is a consulting paper chemist.

Among the subjects under study during the year have been the effect of temperature and relative humidity on the rate of deterioration of paper, and the strength and other characteristics of book papers manufactured during the period 1500-1799. The Laboratory has also given assistance:

- in the development of a permanent/durable book paper for use in the 610-volume pre-1956 National Union Catalog now in process of publication under the sponsorship of the American Library Association;
- in the development of resizing techniques for treatment of paper in connection with the restoration program in the flood-damaged Florentine libraries;
- to the Library of Congress in measuring the deterioration that has occurred in government publications.

In an investigation of the physical strength of modern non-fiction book papers conducted in 1957-58 under the sponsorship of the Virginia State Library with the assistance of the Council, Mr. Barrow concluded that "most library books printed in the first half of the 20th century will be in an unusable condition in the next century."⁵² At the time of his death Mr. Barrow had

⁵¹ XI: 45-49.

⁵² Randolph W. Church, editor. *Deterioration of Book Stock, Causes and Remedies: Two Studies on the Permanence of Book Paper Conducted by W. J. Barrow*. Richmond, Virginia, The Virginia State Library, 1959. p. 16.

completed his investigation of books of the preceding century. The report, since issued,⁵³ is based on examination of 500 non-fiction books (50 of each decade) published during the nineteenth century and typical of those in American research libraries. He found that the quality of papers, which at the beginning of the century had suffered from the early effects of the industrial revolution, was improving; but in mid-century a sharp setback occurred. Acidity is again identified as the chief cause of deterioration. The principal source of this acidity is discovered to be in alum-rosin size, which affects both rag and wood pulp papers. The report establishes that in mid-century the use of alum-rosin size was becoming general at the same time that wood pulp was being substituted for rag fiber as the raw material of paper. Wood pulp, the more obvious factor, has taken the major blame for deterioration which in reality should be laid in great part at the door of the less discernible alum-rosin size.

Progressive deterioration in quality throughout the century is indicated by the sample: 5 per cent of the 1800-1849 papers examined, 10 per cent of the 1850-69 papers, and 37 per cent of the 1870-99 papers are now in the restoration category. Forty-eight per cent of the papers in the last decade of the century, 1890-99, stand in need of restoration.

The report of a smaller study also appeared this year. It is concerned with the permanence of tissue used in the lamination of weakened documents with cellulose acetate film for purposes of reinforcement.⁵⁴

Treatment of Bookworms The Arab Baptist Seminary near Beirut owns a collection of books in Arabic which had become badly infested with bookworms. The dissection of a randomly selected book revealed 319 larvae, whereas the rate of infestation at the American University of Beirut was only 13 per book. James C. Allen, Acting Chairman of the Department of Environmental Health in the University's School of Public Health, is seeking to determine the value of an insecticide in eradicating the infestation and to gain some knowledge of how long the insecticide remains effective. The substance chosen is Diazinon which, among other advantages, is locally available. The investigation involves treating the covers of the books, some of which are rare and irreplaceable, determining the amount of penetration, and periodically dissecting groups of the books to learn if they remain free from reinfestation. The Council has made a small grant to meet local rebinding costs; the University is defraying other expenses.

⁵³ *Strength and Other Characteristics of Book Papers 1800-1899*. Richmond, Virginia, W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, 1967. 116 p.

⁵⁴ W. J. Barrow and Ann M. Carlton. "Permanence of Laminating Tissue." *American Archivist* 31: 88-91, January 1968.

Care and Repair of Books Publication of *Cleaning and Preserving Bindings and Related Materials*, by Mrs. Carolyn Horton, a well known New York expert in the field of conservation of library collections, occurred during the fiscal year.⁵⁵

The work, for which a grant had been made,⁵⁶ is the first fascicle in a series planned to constitute a manual on the care of books and other library materials. Techniques for cleaning leather and clothbound books, procedures for attachment of loose materials, and related matters are discussed; various leather preservatives and other materials are appraised. Another Council grant to the American Library Association enabled the Library Technology Program to arrange for several additional works on such subjects as the repair of leather, vellum, and parchment bindings, and the treatment of materials after fire or water damage. The series is under the general guidance of an advisory committee headed by Harold W. Tribolet, of Chicago.

Russian Studies in Preservation Mrs. Horton's book is of as much interest to the book collector as it is to the professional librarian. Much more technical is another work. With the cooperation of the National Science Foundation the Council was able to arrange for the translation and publication of *Preservation of Documents and Papers (Problema Dolgovechnosti Dokumentov i Bumagi)*, a collection of papers published in 1964 under the auspices of the Laboratory for the Preservation and Restoration of Documents (LKRД) of the Academy of Sciences of the USSR.⁵⁷ The studies are concerned with the aging of papers, preservation, new materials and methods of restoration, new methods of examination of documents, and other related subjects. The Council several years ago initiated the translation and publication of two similar collections of Russian studies in the field.⁵⁸

XI. RESOURCES

Medieval Manuscripts in Microfilm As the number of graduate students and doctoral programs increase, American scholars are finding it more difficult to obtain copies of manuscripts from European libraries, short of making a trip to Europe and concluding arrangements at each location. The Medieval Studies Committee of the University of Pennsylvania

⁵⁵ Chicago, Library Technology Program, American Library Association, 1967. 96 p. 28 cm.

⁵⁶ X: 56.

⁵⁷ D. M. Flyate, editor. *Preservation of Documents and Papers*. Published Pursuant to an Agreement with The United States Department of Commerce, The National Science Foundation and The Council on Library Resources, Inc., Washington, D. C. Jerusalem, Israel Program for Scientific Translations, 1968. vi, 134 p. (Distributed by the Clearinghouse for Federal Scientific and Technical Information. 5285 Port Royal Road, Springfield, Virginia 22151. Order No. TT67-51400.)

⁵⁸ IX: 32.

proposes to establish at the University a central archive of microfilms of manuscripts in European institutions for the use of American scholarship. The collection would include source materials in all areas of research. The Council has made a grant to the University for the first steps in planning the repository.

Coordination of Foreign Manuscript Copying The Center for the Coordination of Foreign Manuscript Copying, located at the Library of Congress, was established in 1965 with the assistance of a Council grant.⁵⁹ The Center seeks to coordinate photocopying projects conducted by American institutions and scholars in foreign archival collections and libraries, thus preventing unwitting duplication of effort. It also provides information about photocopies of collections of foreign manuscripts now in the United States, about extensive photocopying projects in progress or planned, and about which foreign collections are available for copying. The Center is also interested in the organization of consortiums for microfilming projects. In one of two issues of the Center's News to appear this fiscal year the holdings of a number of European archives are briefly described; in the other are listed photocopying projects in progress or recently completed.⁶⁰

Oriental Studies The XXVII International Congress of Orientalists was held at the University of Michigan August 13-19, 1967, as a feature of the University's sesquicentennial year. This was the first meeting in the 94-year history of the Congress to be held in North America and the attendance was the largest: 2,463 specialists representing more than 50 nations. It was also the first time that a panel of librarians was a feature of the program. A gratifying number of scholars demonstrated their awareness of the importance of adequate library resources by attending various sessions of the panel. A grant from the Council provided travel funds for a number of librarians from eastern countries.⁶¹ An account of the panel proceedings has been published.⁶²

Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections The Library of Congress began compilation of the National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections in 1958 with financial assistance from the Council.⁶³ Since 1964 the program has been carried on with Congressional appropriations, and the balance of the Council's final 1963 grant being allocated for promotion of cooperation in the project. The fourth and fifth volumes of the

⁵⁹ IX: 24; XI: 38-39.

⁶⁰ *News From the Center* [for the Coordination of Foreign Manuscript Copying]. No. 2: Fall 1967. 20 p.; No. 3: Spring 1968. 33 l. Library of Congress.

⁶¹ XI: 40.

⁶² Edwin G. Beal, Jr. "Report on the XXVII International Congress on Orientalists in Ann Arbor . . ." *Library of Congress Information Bulletin*. Appendix I, p. 577-79, August 24, 1967.

⁶³ X: 20.

catalog have now been published.⁶⁴ Publication of the fifth volume brought under bibliographic control a total of 18,417 collections in repositories in the 50 states, District of Columbia, and Canal Zone. Also illustrative of the coverage of this continuing series is the fact that the general index in the fifth volume, which cumulates the indexes of the two preceding, gives approximately 88,400 references to an estimated 45,600 subjects and places, 29,200 personal names, and 13,600 corporate bodies.

XII. TESTING AND STANDARDIZATION

Library Technology Program Since its establishment in 1958, the Library Technology Program, nucleus of the American Library Association's Office for Research and Development, has provided a continuing program of testing and standardization of supplies, equipment, systems, and collaboration with industry in the development of improved or new products. Some of its findings are reported in regular columns of the *ALA Bulletin* and *Special Libraries* while other information appears in its bimonthly subscription service, *Library Technology Reports*, or in separate publications. The Program also provides an information service for inquirers. The Council this year, as it has from LTP's beginnings, made grants for the operating budget and for individual projects. However, the Program is developing other sources of income; the Council's 1967-68 contribution to the operating budget represented 43 per cent of its total in contrast with 58 per cent the preceding year.⁶⁵ A management study by Booz, Allen and Hamilton, Inc., now under way, is expected to further the Program's effort to become self-supporting as well as to identify any changes in direction which may appear to be desirable.

In the section on "Photographic Applications" reference was made to an evaluation of microform readers prepared for the Program, and in the section on "Preservation" to a series of works on the care and repair of books. Another project, begun and completed during the fiscal year, was an evaluation of photocopy and microform equipment by William R. Hawken Associates, published in various issues of *Library Technology Reports*.⁶⁶ Two

⁶⁴*The National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections, 1965* . . . Compiled by the Library of Congress From Reports Provided by American Repositories With Assistance From the Council on Library Resources, Inc. Washington, The Library of Congress, 1966. 701 p. 29 cm.

— 1966; *Index 1963-66* . . . Washington, The Library of Congress, 1967. 920 p.

⁶⁵XI: 40.

⁶⁶Among other equipment evaluated in this publication, which has approximately a thousand subscribers here and abroad, during the year, have been electric and manual typewriters, conventional and contemporary steel office desks and secretarial posture chairs, bracket type steel shelving, steel filing cabinets, and record players.

other programs initiated during the year have been concerned with wood card-catalog cabinets, being tested by Buyers Laboratory, Inc., and with audiovisual equipment (16 mm. motion picture projectors, filmstrip-slide projectors, and magnetic tape recorders and tape players), being tested by the United States Testing Company, Inc., under conditions simulating institutional use. Incident to the preparation of a manual on copying methods and equipment,⁶⁷ a study was made of typography in relation to legibility.

Two major monographs in the LTP Publications series appeared during the year. One of these is a comprehensive manual on the selection and maintenance of floors.⁶⁸ It describes the properties of the major categories of floors and floor coverings — resilient, carpet, masonry, wood, and formed-in-place — and explains installation and maintenance techniques. The other monograph, *Compact Library Shelving*,⁶⁹ is basically a translation of a work by a Czech author, Drahoslav Gawrecki, with additional material by other experts, including Robert H. Muller, Associate Director of the University of Michigan Library, who wrote the foreword. Despite the space problems experienced by American libraries, only limited research and discussion have been directed to the subject in the United States. The author discusses the general characteristics of compact shelves — revolving, drawer-type, and sliding compact shelves — and new developments in the USSR and Czechoslovakia.

Library Statistics It is always amazing to note how long some completely obvious shortcomings, reasonably susceptible to resolution, can persist before something is done about them. Such had been the case with respect to library statistics. As recently as 1961, when there were more than 150 major recurring library statistical surveys, it was difficult, when not impossible, to use them for comparative purposes because of the lack of uniformly used definitions or terminology. When the American Library Association, the Special Libraries Association, the American Standards Institute, the Association of Research Libraries, and the U.S. Office of Education decided to cooperate in sponsoring a study to develop standardization, the Council in mid-1963 made a grant for the purpose.⁷⁰ This was supplemented by a grant from the National Science Foundation and assistance from the National Library of Medicine. The project resulted in the publication of a handbook of definitions and terminology,⁷¹

⁶⁷ XI: 27-28.

⁶⁸ Bernard Berkeley. *Floors: Selection and Maintenance*. Chicago, Library Technology Program, American Library Association, 1968. x, 316 p.

⁶⁹ Drahoslav Gawrecki. *Compact Library Shelving*. Translated by Stanislav Rehak. Chicago, Library Technology Program, American Library Association, 1968. xiii, 185 p.

⁷⁰ VII: 31-32. See also: IX: 39-40; X: 24, 57-58.

⁷¹ *Library Statistics: A Handbook of Concepts, Definitions, and Terminology*. Prepared by the Staff of Statistics Coordinating Project. Joel Williams, Director. Chicago, American Library Association, 1966.

and the convening of a national conference to discuss their adoption. The proceedings of the conference were published this past fiscal year.⁷²

UNESCO, responsible for the collection and publication of international library statistics, was experiencing a similar problem. The International Standards Organization (ISO), aware of American developments in this area, became interested. The Council therefore made a grant to the American Standards Institute in 1965 to promote international standardization through a meeting of representatives of ISO, the International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA), and UNESCO.⁷³ Since preliminary results were encouraging, the Council again made a grant this fiscal year to IFLA for a joint meeting of its statistics committee with that of ISO and with interested officials of UNESCO. A final text of an international standard for library statistics may be recommended to the member nations for acceptance at the 1970 UNESCO General Conference.

XIII. CLR FELLOWSHIP PROGRAM

A CLR- Administered Program

The nature of librarianship is broadening and becoming more complex, making demands on the profession well beyond the traditional ones. Recognizing this, the Council has made plans for a Fellowship Program to provide candidates considered to have a potential for leadership with an opportunity to familiarize themselves with the changes occurring in the administrative and technical aspects of librarianship and thus serve more usefully in their own institutions. The program will be limited to about 15 librarians the first year, and it is planned to give the same opportunity to a like number in the two succeeding years. The intent of the program precludes grants to those who are primarily concerned with working toward an advanced degree.

The grants will be for a period of from three to 12 months and will cover all extraordinary expenses such as travel, per diem, supplies and equipment. It is hoped that an awardee's institution will recognize the benefits that can accrue to it from his experiences under the grant and provide him with leave with pay. Louis B. Wright, Vice-Chairman of the Council's Board of Directors, is chairman of the Fellowship Program. The names of the first group of Fellows are to be announced in the spring of 1969.

⁷² Alphonse F. Trezza and James Beasely, editors. *National Conference on Library Statistics. A Conference Co-Sponsored by the Library Division/American Library Association and the National Center for Educational Statistics, United States Office of Education, June 6-8, 1966. Chicago, Illinois. Chicago, American Library Association, 1967. 100 p.*

⁷³ X: 57-58.

FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

Opinion of Independent Accountants

July 26, 1968

To the Board of Directors of
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

In our opinion, the accompanying financial statements (Exhibits I-III) present fairly the assets, liabilities and fund balance of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1968, its expenditures and income and sources and applications of cash for the year, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles applied on a basis consistent with that of the preceding year. Our examination of these statements was made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary in the circumstances.

Our examination was made primarily for the purpose of forming our opinion on the financial statements, taken as a whole. We also examined the supplementary statement of grants, contracts and Council-administered projects (Exhibit IV) by similar auditing procedures. In our opinion, this supplementary information is stated fairly in all material respects in relation to the financial statements, taken as a whole. Although not essential for a fair presentation of the information set forth in Exhibits I-III, this information is submitted as additional data.

PRICE WATERHOUSE & CO.

EXHIBIT I

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
STATEMENT OF ASSETS, LIABILITIES
AND FUND BALANCE

ASSETS	June 30	
	1968	1967
Cash (see Exhibit III)	\$ 118,982	\$ 232,057
Investments:		
United States Treasury Bills, at cost plus discount earned (approximates market)	290,332	297,227
Savings account		514,974
Certificates of deposit, at cost plus accrued interest ..	762,142	611,077
Grant receivable from The Ford Foundation in quarterly instalments of \$250,000 (Note)	1,000,000	1,750,000
Prepaid expenses and deposits	2,278	580
	<u>\$2,173,734</u>	<u>\$3,405,915</u>

LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE

Grants and contracts payable (see Exhibit IV)	632,685	977,571
Accounts payable, accrued salaries and withheld taxes	9,144	7,786
	<u>641,829</u>	<u>985,357</u>
Fund balance:		
Balance beginning of year	2,420,558	3,595,756
Deduct—Expenditures less income for the year (see Exhibit II)	888,653	1,175,198
Balance end of year (Note)	1,531,905	2,420,558
	<u>\$2,173,734</u>	<u>\$3,405,915</u>

NOTE

Effective July 1, 1968, The Ford Foundation has approved an additional \$5,000,000 grant to the Council for the continuation and expansion of the Council's program. The new grant agreement specifies that the remaining balance of the current grant and the new grant will be expended in substantial compliance with an annual budget of \$2,000,000 for a three year period beginning July 1, 1968, and that the new grant will be disbursed in quarterly instalments. At June 30, 1968, \$1,623,121 had been appropriated by the Board of Directors for specific grants and contracts and \$100,000 has been allocated to the President for future grants and contracts of up to \$25,000 each to be made at his discretion. Certain of these appropriations satisfy the terms of the current Ford Foundation grant whereby \$200,000 annually is earmarked for the creation of a laboratory. The excess of appropriated amounts over the Fund balance is attributable to appropriations made after receiving notification from The Ford Foundation of the grant which became effective July 1, 1968.

EXHIBIT II

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
 STATEMENT OF EXPENDITURES AND INCOME

EXPENDITURES	For the Year Ended June 30	
	1968	1967
Grants, contracts and Council-administered projects (see Exhibit IV)	\$ 689,609	\$1,124,389
Less: Adjustments resulting from excess allocations in grants awarded (see Exhibit IV)	<u>42,965</u>	<u>45,785</u>
	<u>646,644</u>	<u>1,078,604</u>
General administrative expense:		
Compensation and employee benefits	196,705	134,427
Rent	13,225	10,850
Professional services	40,784	7,202
Travel and meetings	17,730	10,997
Furniture and equipment	12,733	1,175
Printing and duplication	6,529	8,671
Office and other expenses	<u>17,849</u>	<u>9,302</u>
	<u>305,555</u>	<u>182,624</u>
	952,199	1,261,228
 INCOME		
From investments	<u>63,546</u>	<u>86,030</u>
Expenditures less income	<u>\$ 888,653</u>	<u>\$1,175,198</u>

EXHIBIT III

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
 STATEMENT OF SOURCE AND
 APPLICATION OF CASH

	For the Year Ended June 30	
	1968	1967
Cash provided by:		
Receipts from Ford Foundation	\$ 750,000	\$ 250,000
Proceeds from disposition of investment securities	2,180,930	2,266,080
Savings account drawings	533,769	250,000
Grant refunds	25,245	34,420
	<u>3,489,944</u>	<u>2,800,500</u>
Cash applied to:		
Grant payments	1,016,775	977,000
General and administrative expenses	305,745	177,046
Purchases of investment securities	2,280,349	1,196,370
Savings account additions		500,000
Employee travel advances, net	150	92
	<u>3,603,019</u>	<u>2,850,508</u>
Cash decrease during the year	(113,075)	(50,008)
Cash, beginning of year	<u>232,057</u>	<u>282,065</u>
Cash, end of year	<u>\$ 118,982</u>	<u>\$ 232,057</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
STATEMENT OF GRANTS, CONTRACTS AND
COUNCIL-ADMINISTERED PROJECTS

Year Ended June 30, 1968

	Payable June 30, 1967	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1968
American Council of Learned Societies					
Review of foreign acquisitions under Public Law 480	\$ 9,500			\$ 9,500	
Study of the problems and needs of research libraries	19,650			19,650	
American Historical Association					
Assistance to Joint Committee on Status of the National Archives			\$ 104	(104)	
American Library Association					
Assistance in establishing a quarterly Journal of Information Science and Library Automation ..	21,009			10,325	\$ 10,684
Assistance to Special Subcommittee on Aid to Italian Libraries		\$ 1,000		1,000	
Development of guidelines for book purchasing procedures and for determining qualifications of library book vendors bidding on contracts ..			2,046	(2,046)	
Evaluation of the work of the Library Technology Program		19,000			19,000
Library Technology Project (Program)					
Projects of testing and standardization to June 30, 1965	7,500		9,375	(1,875)	
Projects of testing and standardization to June 30, 1966			2,351	(2,351)	
Projects of testing and standardization to August 31, 1967	152,503		10,125	75,527	66,851
Extension of Library Technology Program to August 31, 1968	96,200			48,100	48,100
Conservation of Library Materials, Phase II		30,000			30,000
Director's Discretionary Fund, September 1, 1967 - August 31, 1968		10,000		5,000	5,000
Preparation of a manuscript reporting the results of an analytic and comparative study of typography and legibility		6,250		6,250	
A program for evaluating photocopy and microform equipment for libraries		16,500		16,500	
Publication of a book-selection service (Choice) at the college library level	75,975			44,125	31,850
Studies in connection with the work of the Committee on Copyright Issues		4,993		4,993	
A study of systems of public libraries			60	(60)	
Support of the ALA International Relations Office		10,000		10,000	
Association of American Law Schools					
Preparation of book selection lists for law school libraries (continuation)		29,810		29,810	

	Payable June 30, 1967	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1968
Association of Research Libraries					
First (pilot) phase in a National Preservation Program for research library materials			\$10,078	\$ (10,078)	
A study of lighting requirements for libraries		\$ 4,500		4,500	
American University of Beirut					
Decontamination of insect-infested books		250		250	
W. J. Barrow Laboratory					
Establishment of a laboratory for investigations relative to the preservation of books and other library materials	\$103,405			58,193	\$ 45,212
Bell & Howell Company					
Development of a step-and-repeat camera for producing microimages by Xerography	9,070				9,070
Boston University					
Conference on university library standards, November 2-3, 1967		2,468	297	2,171	
Expenses of testing a coordinate index to legal literature*	1,827		1,371	456	
Free Library of Philadelphia					
Development and field-testing of a theft protection system		66,500		33,250	33,250
XXVII International Congress of Orientalists (Association for Asian Studies, fiscal agent)					
Program on library resources for Oriental studies			3,065	(3,065)	
International Federation of Library Associations					
Completion of international standardization of library statistics		3,500		3,500	
International Council on Archives					
Implementation of the resolutions of the Extraordinary Congress of the International Council on Archives, Washington, May 1966 ..	8,600			8,600	
Joint Committee on the Union List of Serials					
Assistance to National Serials Data Program		30,000			30,000
Library of Congress					
Development of procedures for automated control of thematic map collections		33,537		16,768	16,769
Establishment of a center for the coordination of foreign manuscript copying	25,100			25,100	
Establishment of National Register of Microform Masters office and publication of the first volume of information collected by it			677	(677)	
MARC Participants Meeting at the Library of Congress		2,000	353	1,647	
Support of the work of the Federal Library Committee (supplement)	32,550			32,550	
London University, School of Librarianship and Archives					
Preparation of a catalog code for materials in Hindi		7,000		3,500	3,500

*Council-administered project

	Payable June 30, 1967	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1968
Los Angeles County Public Library					
Investigation of the use of optical character recognition equipment in library operations	\$ 10,000			\$ 4,669	\$ 5,331
Massachusetts Institute of Technology					
Project Intrex — experiments in text access and related exploratory research	125,000			125,000	
Project Intrex — June 1-November 1, 1968		\$162,500		162,500	
Meeting on circulation of books by mail, Sheraton Palace Hotel, San Francisco, California, June 24-25, 1967*	1,858		\$ 772	1,086	
R. A. Morgan Company					
Construction and testing of a prototype of a bibliographer's camera	22,386			7,500	14,886
Mt. San Antonio College Foundation					
Development of a teaching machine for instruction in use of library tools (revised project)		10,000		5,000	5,000
National Archives and Records Service					
Computer indexing and composition of archival/manuscript finding aids	40,000			19,000	21,000
New England Board of Higher Education					
Development of a computer-based regional technical processing center for cataloging information					
Tasks 2, 3 and 4 — Development of programs for file searching; development of programs for acquisitions processing; pilot operation of the center	100,000	168,271		145,000	123,271
Pennsylvania State University (formerly reported as Modern Language Association of America)					
Assistance to International Conference on Bibliographic Form and Style	5,000			5,000	
Purdue Research Foundation, Division of Sponsored Programs, Lafayette, Indiana					
Characteristics of library collections which affect their support of graduate education ..		5,039		5,039	
Republic Aviation Division, Fairchild Hiller					
Analysis and verification program for utilizing the Micro-Vue System for reducing the cost of distribution of library materials	32,885			32,885	
San Antonio Public Library					
Books-by-mail public library circulation system ..		22,500		5,000	17,500
Professor Richard H. Shoemaker, Graduate School of Library Science, Rutgers — The State University					
Support of a Checklist of American Imprints ..		2,500		2,500	

*Council-administered project

	Payable June 30, 1967	Grant, Contract or Project	Adjust- ments	Payments (Refunds)	Payable June 30, 1968
Society of American Archivists					
Archives and records center buildings and equipment — a volume of selected papers		\$ 1,000		\$ 1,000	
Support for Guy R. Lyle's study of library duplication of special collections and of the need for a code of practice for reprint publishers; and other library programs*		1,500			\$ 1,500
Taylor-Merchant Corporation					
Development of a portable projector for microfiches, microfilm	\$ 500			500	
University of California					
Preparation and publication of a handbook on data processing for libraries	34,249				34,249
University of California at Berkeley					
Experiment in library application of facsimile transmission equipment, Phase 2		2,000		2,000	
University of California at Los Angeles					
To test and evaluate, in practical application, a step-and-repeat camera developed by Houston Fearless Corporation			\$ 2,291	(2,291)	
University of California at Santa Cruz					
Development of a universal and machine-manipulable classification scheme for slide collections		18,841		4,710	14,131
University of Chicago					
Study of patterns in the use of research library materials	24,600				24,600
University of Illinois					
Preparation of a manual of university archival practice with respect to records of academic scientific research	5,000			5,000	
University of North Carolina (on behalf of American Standards Association Sectional Committee Z39)					
Development of standards in library work and documentation	12,300				12,300
University of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia					
Planning a central repository of microfilms of European medieval manuscripts		3,150		3,150	
Various*					
Expenses connected with the "Laboratory"	904	10,000		4,701	6,203
Travel grants to attend meetings abroad		5,000		1,572	3,428
	<u>\$977,571</u>	<u>\$689,609</u>	<u>\$42,965</u>	<u>\$991,530</u>	<u>\$632,685</u>

*Council-administered project

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The scholar at his book-wheel, which appears on the title-page, is reproduced from an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine*, Paris, 1588. The picture has appeared in the Council's Third and subsequent annual reports. The simplified drawing of the picture, appearing on the cover, was prepared by George Lohr for use with the Council's mailing meter die.

The picture of "Checkpoint" is used with the permission of the Free Library of Philadelphia; Metal Edge Industries, Barrington, New Jersey, and Logistics Industries Corporation, Philadelphia.

The picture of the mailing desk at the San Antonio Public Library is used with the permission of the Library.

The picture of brittle books being removed from the shelves at the Library of Congress is used with the permission of the *Washington Post* (Margaret Thomas, photographer).

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Council on Library Resources.

Report. 1st-

1956/57-

Washington.

v. 23 cm. annual.

Report year ends June 30.

1. Library science—Research.

Z673.C96A15

020.624

58-915 rev

Library of Congress

